

DIAGNOSTIC ASSESSMENT IN LEARNING

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Abstract

Diagnostic assessments play an important role in supporting an inclusive and differentiated approach to education, where education is tailored to students' varying ability levels and needs. Diagnostic assessment is an assessment process carried out with the aim of identifying individual student learning characteristics, competencies, strengths and weaknesses. The main aim of a diagnostic assessment is to understand more deeply the students' abilities, understanding, level of knowledge and needs in the learning context. Diagnostic assessments can involve a variety of assessment methods, including tests, observations, interviews, or observing student behavior. The results of the diagnostic assessment are used to assist educators and teachers in designing learning that suits students' needs and ability levels. Thus, diagnostic assessment is an important tool in curriculum development and effective education delivery.

Keywords: Diagnostic Assessment, Learning Assessment, Assessment Methods.

BACKGROUND OF STUDY

Diagnostic assessment is a form of assessment that is carried out specifically with the aim of identifying the characteristics, competencies, strengths, and weaknesses of student learning. This allows educators to understand students individually and design learning to suit their needs. As stated in Kepmendikbud No.719/P / 2020.

Diagnostic assessment is an independent Curriculum Assessment/assessment that is carried out specifically with the aim of identifying or knowing the characteristics, competency conditions, strengths, weaknesses of student learning models, so that learning can be designed in accordance with the competencies and conditions of diverse students.

Along with the enactment of the policy, the ability to conduct diagnostic assessments has become a new major challenge for teachers. Diagnostic assessment is one of the assessment tools as a distinctive feature of The Independent curriculum. Diagnostic assessment provides significant benefits for teachers. By understanding students better, teachers can design more appropriate methods, models, and Learning media. This increases the chances of student success in achieving learning goals. As such, diagnostic assessment is a powerful tool to enhance student learning and assist teachers in designing more effective and relevant learning experiences.

Basically, the implementation of diagnostic assessment can provide its own spirit for teachers. If teachers are more involved in the learning process, then teachers can provide more appropriate support to students, and can more easily see the positive results of their

efforts. Diagnostic assessments also allow personalization of learning. Teachers can design a learning plan that is more suited to the needs and ability levels of each student. Teachers can help to reach the maximum potential of students. However, the reality on the ground shows that most teachers are still confused and do not even know how to carry out diagnostic assessments, especially for teachers and principals who do not follow the driving school program or driving teacher.

The Ministry of Education, Culture, Research and Technology (Kemendikbud Ristek) reports that there are already around 142,000 schools in Indonesia that are willing to use the Independent curriculum independently in the 2022/2023 academic year. That is, there are differences that underlie schools in implementing independent curricula. Schools that register for the independent path program have not received IKM training, considering that this curriculum has only been applied to schools that are ready, namely schools that have received training through the driving school program. That is, schools or teachers who have not received training, certainly have not received knowledge about diagnostic assessment. The results of the study (Arini Maut, 2002:1305) stated that based on the results of the analysis of the readiness of teachers in implementing diagnostic assessment on independent curriculum obtained the following data : as a result of the written interview form that teachers stated never heard the term diagnostic assessment, 3 teachers expressed hesitation and 5 teachers stated never heard the term diagnostic assessment.

RESEARCH METHOD

The research method used is qualitative descriptive method. The research was conducted by looking for facts about how the implementation of curriculum development in mathematics learning. The results of the study in the form of descriptions of various problems that occur in the field, including observing the activities, views, attitudes, and processes that take place during the study, and interpret the research findings appropriately. As Sugiyono (2012) states that:

Qualitative descriptive research is intended to describe and describe the phenomena that exist, both natural and Human Engineering, which pay more attention to the characteristics, quality, interrelations between activities. In addition, descriptive research does not provide treatment, manipulation or alteration of the variables studied, but rather describes a condition as it is. The only treatment given was the study itself, which was carried out through observation, interviews and documentation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Diagnostic assessment is one component that supports the implementation of the independent curriculum. In this context, diagnostic assessment helps teachers in adapting learning materials according to the characteristics and abilities of students, which is in line with the spirit of flexibility of the independent curriculum. With the implementation of diagnostic assessment in schools has provided many positive things to the spirit of its own for teachers, so that teachers can adjust and design methods,

models and learning media that match the ability of students to deliver learning achievement material. So the main purpose of diagnostic assessment is to help teachers understand students more deeply. Thus, teachers can design learning that is more effective and in accordance with the level of ability and condition of diverse students. Diagnostic assessments map the ability of all students in the classroom quickly, to find out who already understands, who is somewhat understood, and who does not understand. Thus the teacher can adjust the learning material to the ability of students. Diagnostic assessment can be divided into two, namely cognitive diagnostic assessment and non-cognitive diagnostic assessment. Cognitive diagnostic assessment aims to diagnose the basic abilities of students on the topic of a subject. The cognitive diagnostic assessment may contain one or more subject topics.

The objectives of the cognitive diagnosis assessment are as follows: 1) Identify the achievement of student competence, 2) Adjust classroom learning to the average competence of students, 3) provide remedial classes or additional lessons to students with below average competence. Assessment of cognitive diagnosis through several stages, from preparation, implementation, and follow-up.

1. Preparation Stage:

- a) Schedule assessment lessons: scheduling a time for diagnostic assessment is an important step. This allows the school and teachers to ensure that all students have sufficient time to work on the assessment calmly and without interruption. This schedule should also take into account the time required to evaluate and analyze the results of the assessment.
- b) Identification of assessment materials: assessment materials must be carefully selected based on the competencies or basic competencies (KD) present in the curriculum. Assessment materials should be relevant to the learning objectives and reflect what has been taught to students.
- c) Make-up questions: make-up assessment questions require special attention. Questions should be clearly designed, easily understood by students, and measure the extent to which students have understood the material taught. In this case, you have provided guidelines for structuring the questions, such as the number of questions and the different levels of difficulty for semester 1 and 2.

2. Implementation Stage:

- a) Distribution of assessment questions: during the implementation phase, the teacher must provide assessment questions to all students in the class. This can be done face-to-face in the classroom or through sending questions online if students are studying from home.
- b) Supervision: if the assessment is carried out face-to-face, the teacher or supervisor must ensure that the assessment process takes place fairly and without fraud. This involves monitoring students as they work on the problems.
- c) Processing time: make sure students have enough time to work on assessment questions according to a predetermined schedule.

- d) Collect assessment results: after students have finished working on the assessment questions, the teacher must collect all the assessment results for further evaluation.
- e) Evaluation and analysis: the results of the assessment should be carefully evaluated and analyzed. This can help teachers to understand the extent to which students have understood the learning material and identify areas where students may need additional help.
- f) Feedback: provide feedback to students on their assessment results. It can help students to understand their strengths and weaknesses in understanding the material.

3. Follow-Up Phase:

- a) Perform diagnostic assessment of assessment results: after collecting the assessment results, the teacher must perform an analysis of these results. This includes evaluating student performance, identifying patterns of strengths and weaknesses, as well as understanding the overall level of class understanding of the material being tested.
- b) Based On the Diagnostic Results, Divide the Students into 3 Groups:
 - 1. students with Class average: students who have performance in line with class average can still be taught by their class teacher.
 - 2. Students 1 Semester below average: students whose performance is one semester below average may require extra attention. They may be placed in lower grades or in study groups that receive additional support, including help from a parent or relevant chaperone.
 - 3. students 2 semesters below average: students whose performance is two semesters below average require special attention. They can also be placed in lower grades or in study groups that receive additional support. In some cases, the accompaniment of a family member or other relevant companion can be very helpful.
- c) Do a learning assessment of the topic already taught: before starting a new learning topic, it is important to do a reassessment of the topic already taught. This allows teachers to ensure that students have understood the material before moving on to new material. This assessment can be a replay, retest, or relevant assignment.

Of the three stages, follow-up diagnostic assessment is an important step in ensuring that learning can take place effectively and that each student will get attention and support according to their ability level. By engaging three different groups of students, teachers can accommodate the diverse needs of students in their classrooms. In addition, a reassessment of the material already taught helps to strengthen students' understanding before moving on to the next material. The non-cognitive diagnostic assessment aims to measure psychological aspects and emotional conditions of learners before starting learning. Thus, the implementation of non-cognitive diagnostic assessment more emphasis on psychological and emotional well-being of learners. Non-cognitive

assessment was conducted to assess the activity of students during home study while still paying attention to their family conditions. Related to the preparation and implementation of non-cognitive diagnostic assessments, the teacher's skill to ask and make questions can help teachers obtain comprehensive and in-depth information. (Mutiani et al., 2020) The preparatory stage is largely determined by the creativity of a teacher to compile diagnostic assessment instruments both cognitive and noncognitive. The implementation stage requires good questioning skills, especially in noncognitive diagnostic assessments that allow teachers to conduct interview methods, or by giving students the opportunity to tell about what are the obstacles they experience. The follow-up stage needs the seriousness of a teacher to really think about the best steps to help students with various difficulties. In this case, the teacher can discuss with the principal or colleagues. If the diagnostic assessment can really be implemented properly and maximally, the implementation of the independent curriculum can also be implemented in schools to the maximum and quality. Hopefully. (Nasution, 2021)

Diagnostic assessment plays an important role in supporting an inclusive and differentiated approach to education, where education is tailored to students' diverse levels of ability and needs. Diagnostic assessment is an assessment process that is carried out with the aim of identifying the characteristics, competencies, strengths, and weaknesses of individual student learning. The main purpose of diagnostic assessment is to understand more about the ability, understanding, level of knowledge, and needs of students in the context of learning. Diagnostic assessment can involve a variety of assessment methods, including tests, observations, interviews, or observations of student behavior. The results of the diagnostic assessment are used to assist educators and teachers in designing learning that suits the needs and ability levels of students. Thus, diagnostic assessment is an important tool in curriculum development and effective education.

CONCLUSION

Diagnostic assessment is a powerful tool to enhance student learning and assist teachers in designing more effective and relevant learning experiences cognitive diagnostic assessment goes through several stages, from preparation, implementation, and follow-up.

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